

Evidence-building for Science & Engineering Workforce Policy

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Abstract

Early in 2022, the National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics (NCSES) established America's DataHub Consortium to build a secure, national data asset for "collaborative research and decision-making." We report here on our progress, as members of this consortium, to create a database of foreign-born scientists and engineers (FBSE) including those who may have received training in the US, but for whom, upon leaving the US, data on work and affiliations in federal databases disappear, thus answering important questions about FBSEs, their characteristics and their contributions the US research and development ecosystem. We describe our data sources; data; data linking process and workflow; risks to data integrity and quality; and our approach to mitigating those risks. In addition to providing the technical details of constructing the database, we will also discuss the nature of the evidence available from these data.

Introduction

The 2022 Edition of the National Science Board's Science and Engineering Indicators shows that Foreign-born Scientists and Engineers (FBSEs) continue to be a critical part of the US science and engineering (S&E) workforce¹. To better understand the participation of the US research workforce, integrated individual-level information is required. Despite legislative efforts intended to codify data transparency, access, and quality to support policymaking, barriers remain in collecting, utilizing, and sharing data on individuals. Gathering and combining relevant data is difficult, and sharing data requires additional care because of risks to confidentiality, privacy, and security.

In this research-in-progress presentation, we describe our work to shed light on active FBSEs, including those who may have received training in the US, but for whom, upon leaving the US, data on work and affiliations in federal databases disappear, thus answering important questions about FBSEs, their characteristics and their contributions the US research and development (R&D) ecosystem. In the project's first phase (to be presented), we focus on a subset of the FBSE population to develop and demonstrate our ability to identify, acquire, link, and analyze the evidence to support policy decisions. Our approach led to a replicable framework that can be scaled in future phases to the available FBSE population or to other segments of the global research workforce.

Our technical efforts to combine individual-level data on FBSEs draw upon and contribute to relevant academic research on topics such as securely linking individuals while preserving privacy and associated challenges encountered in data collection; database interoperability and data quality; and appropriate use of analytical tools and techniques (e.g. artificial intelligence, machine learning and natural language processing); thus enabling the drawing of inferences from blended and integrated data and customizing visualization and dissemination of the findings and evidence to match the needs of multiple audiences. Such important advances in

¹Available at <https://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2020/nsb20222/nsb20222.pdf>

integrating and analyzing individual-level information on the research workforce can inform other strategic priorities such as those articulated in the National Secure Data Service Act of 2021.

Data sources

The following proprietary data sources were used for the research:

- Steppingblocks' proprietary workforce database, including 130+ million individual profiles
- Clarivate's Web of Science scholarly publication database, indexing over 22,000 of the highest quality peer-reviewed journals, across all science & engineering disciplines

The following data sources were requested for validation, subject to government provision:

- Dept of Labor's data on permanent (PERM) and temporary (LCA) work certifications
- Dept of Homeland Security's Student and Exchange Visitor Information System (SEVIS)

Research methodology

Candidate data set creation

To build the initial 35M FBSE candidate data set (outermost circle in Figure 1), we identified potential foreign markers in their 135M+ career profile database. Steppingblocks aggregates and distills data from many publicly available data sources, including social media platforms, online job sites, government sources, and resumes. Parallel computing was used to map hundreds of variables from the FBSE's first job title to their most recent, and everything in between, including variables indicating salary, skills, and educational qualifications.

Institutions were identified from this output but had to be manually reviewed and assessed to build the tagged records for an initial data set (7.49M in the second circle in Figure 1). Steppingblocks drew from their education and job category taxonomies to match the *Science and engineering (S&E) fields* and *Science and engineering (S&E)-related occupations*, as defined in NCSES Glossary¹. This filtering process winnowed the data set to 4.06M individuals with science and engineering degrees of whom 1.34M had identifiable links to organizations (Innermost circles in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Progression of FBSE database development

Validation of candidate profiles

Next we validated the 1.34M candidate profiles. We targeted citizenship and visa information data from the Department of Labor's Office of Foreign Labor Certification (OFLC) and Department of Homeland Security's SEVIS. However, these government data proved to be inaccessible within the project timeline.

We then developed an alternative approach that considered publicly available government OFLC data², where the most relevant data sets were the permanent labor certifications (PERM) and H-1B visa applications (H-1B). These data sets focus on specialty occupations and were thought most likely to match FBSE candidates generated from the initial Steppingblocks' data. Of these options, the period 2016 through 2019 in the publicly available, non-restricted PERM data set was selected as the richer source for linkage.

We chose "Certified," and "Certified-Expired" PERM records for the years 2016-2019 as selection parameters based on data completeness, linkage potential, and expected output volume. The normalized and filtered PERM data set was then linked to the FBSE data set. The first step was an organizational linkage that provided approximately 62% linking rate and yielded 249,182 applications which could be positively linked with Steppingblocks' data. Next, dates of employment in Steppingblocks' database were linked to the decision dates found in the 249,182 PERM records. There was a return of 90.5%, reducing the size of the data set to 225,065 FBSE profiles. Next, similarity computations were employed using these variables:

- Graduation Year (blocking was performed on that variable)
- School Name (We used Jaro Winkler text similarity² to allow for different spellings and variations in how the name was reported.)
- Degree Level (Exact Match)
- Education Major (Cosine Similarity of Sentence Embeddings, BERT)
- Job Title (Cosine Similarity on Sentence Embeddings, BERT)

Distinguishing among many candidates with the same education domain working at the same company and performing the same job function (e.g., Computer Science major, hired at Google as a Software Engineer) required an additional filtering layer used a machine learning model to predict ethnicities from potential candidate's full names (when possible).

From that effort, 81,162 profiles were linked to OFLC PERM data sets between 2016 and 2019. Using NCSES criteria for foreign-born scientists or engineers yielded 77,823 FBSE profiles. Considering these data validation measures, we have high confidence in the resulting data set, referred to henceforth as PERM-SB.

Linking to Web of Science

To learn more about the research productivity and research contributions of the FBSEs, we next merged the FBSE candidate population with Clarivate's Web of Science (WoS). Among professional bibliometricians, WoS is considered an unparalleled resource for research into the past, present and future of scholarly research.

²<https://www.dol.gov/agencies/eta/foreign-labor/performance>

Following validation of the PERM-SB data set, we turned to linking it to the WoS data on publications and citations. The first filter initially linked records with a shared last name and first initial. FBSE profiles of individuals with common names yielded multiple matches among the WoS profiles. Of the original data set of 77,823 FBSE profiles, 11,862 FBSEs did not share a common last name or first initial with any WoS profile. Additionally, 3,174 FBSEs lacked an identified last name altogether. The linkage was performed on the remaining 62,787 FBSEs. PERM-SB was linked to WoS profiles using five administrative data variables common to both data sets: institutional email domain name, first name, institutional affiliations, and name commonality. This filtering process yielded 10,550 (16.8%) PERM-SB profiles that matched a unique WOS profile. Another 809 PERM-SB profiles (1.3%) were matched solely on personal email address. This matched data set consisting of 11,359 FBSE profiles is referred to as PERM-SB-WoS and is depicted in the center of the Venn diagram in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Venn diagram depicting relationships among the OFLC PERM data set, Steppingblocks FBSE profiles and the Web of Science

Results and discussion

Linkage and validation

At the onset of the project, Steppingblocks examined the data collected in their processes to select those observations for their Extraction, Transformation, and Loading (ETL) process, using the following criteria for inclusion:

- Any location markers outside the US, e.g., job, training, and education locations.
- Languages e.g., Korean
- Group membership, awards, or projects linked to foreign populations, e.g., “Association of Chinese Students and Scholars at Yale” or “ALPFA.org | Latino Professionals for America”

Foreign institutions and degree programs were identified in the first FBSE profiles, but this information often followed native language and norms and was not easily mapped to US degrees and naming conventions.

Cases of US students who were studying in a foreign country or US entities with foreign campuses, for example, also posed an unexpected impediment. For instance, the use of foreign

markers as an initial screen identified: a) US students studying abroad, b) military personnel, c) US expatriates, d) enrollees in foreign campuses of US universities, e.g., the degree granting foreign campuses³ of New York University in Abu Dhabi or Shanghai.

There are several government databases that have reliable information for validating our selection process by verifying that the candidates were indeed FBSE. However, we were not granted access to such data, so we sought publicly available information that could be used to verify that we were correctly identifying FBSEs. Publicly available government data such as the OFLC H-1B visa applications data have ninety-six distinct variables for each applicant. Of these, thirteen variables were identified for linking that could potentially allow us to distinguish between different individuals who started working for the same company around the same date. The PERM data sets have even more data than the H-1B set, with up to 154 variables for each case, including sponsoring employers, intended employee positions, previous education, and country of birth/citizenship. After careful review, nine PERM variables were identified for linkage.

Although better results were possible with the PERM data versus the H-1B data, certain challenges persisted, including self-reporting on fields such as job title, and employer. In linking the FBSE data set with WoS, challenges were noted in self-reported variable spellings or omissions of FBSE first names (e.g., name with diacritics transliterated), inconsistent use of a middle initial, and variations in self-reported institutional affiliation name.

As each data source was assessed and incorporated, assumptions and options were reviewed and biases inherent in the data were identified. Identifying FBSEs using the methods devised resulted in a preponderance of FBSEs who stayed and worked in the United States.

Despite excellent classification accuracy and an F1-score^{5,6} of 0.86, our model is heavily biased towards accurately identifying only the most common ethnic groups represented in the US.

While the PERM data provided the greatest potential for linkage, it has a built-in bias towards H-1B profiles⁷, individuals with advanced degrees and in specialized areas. 2016-2019 public PERM records were used as they offered the most consistent and recent data to maximize our chances of a good link.

Each PERM record had a case status with four possible outcomes: Certified, Certified-Expired, Denied, and Withdrawn. Applications with the status of Denied or Withdrawn could have been denied or withdrawn for various reasons, including data inaccuracy, so these were filtered out. The resulting data set numbered 406,921 individual applications after this initial filtering.

Furthermore, to increase chances of generating high-quality matches, only records that could be linked directly to Steppingblocks' list of organizations were selected, which generated a slight bias towards larger organizations.

Identifying FBSEs using the methods devised thus far result in a bias towards FBSEs who stayed and worked in the United States. A simple volumetric analysis shows that in 2019, for every certified PERM application, roughly twice as many H-1Bs visas and four times as many student⁸ visas (F or M) were granted.

We successfully matched 11,359 individuals from the PERM-SB data set to WoS publications to generate a new PERM-SB-WoS data set. Biographical information from the two data sources enabled us to establish the linkage between PERM-SB and WoS and to provide information about FBSE publication productivity and impact, and their research topic area. As shown in

Table 1, there is at least 97% coverage for each field provided by the PERM-SB-WoS data set. That is, at least 97% of records have a valid value for each WoS variable.

Table 1. Percentage coverage of the bibliometric fields in PERM-SB-WoS

Field	Coverage
Number of Publications	100%
Impact Percentile	99.95%
Research Topic	97.65%
Collaborating Country	99.89%

The linkage between PERM-SB and WoS is predicated on the individual's having published. The PERM-SB-WoS data set contains FBSEs who have published in peer-reviewed journals.

Data representativeness

Having established the feasibility of creating a high quality and procedurally valid FBSE data set, we assessed representativeness of the data. In Table 2, the distribution of the visa types confirms that our linked data set (78K) is biased towards H-1B visa holders.

Table 2. Evaluation of representation against PERM 2016-2019 data set

Visa type (Top 5)	2016-2019 PERM (N=~446,000)	PERM-SB data set (n=~78,000)
H-1B	0.701	0.813
L-1	0.069	0.078
F-1	0.059	0.062
TN	0.018	0.017
Outside US	0.034	0.006
Other	0.057	0.016

Given the preponderance of H-1B visas, usually issued for high-tech industries, we note that the PERM-SB data set over-represents those with Computer Science and Engineering majors (as shown in Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of individuals represented in SB and PERM-SB

Majors (Top 5)	FBSE (%) (N=1.34 million)	PERM-SB (%) (n=78,000)	Representation Ratio
Computer Engineering	1.8	5.2	2.88
Electronics Engineering	1.9	5.0	2.61
Electrical Engineering	4.4	10.9	2.50
Computer Science	9.8	21.2	2.15
Engineering	5.9	8.0	1.37

Hence, the PERM-SB data set is not representative of the full FBSE population. Because the WoS data set has only published researchers, the PERM-SB-WoS data set is likely to over-

represent doctorates. Table 4 shows the overall proportion of highest degree levels among all degree holders for the PERM-SB and PERM-SB-WoS data, confirming that observation.

Table 4. Highest Degree Level between the PERM and PERM-SB-WoS data sets

Highest Degree Level	Percent of PERM-SB data set	Percent of PERM-SB-WoS data set	Representation Ratio
Bachelor's or Master's	89.0	57.1	0.64
Doctorate	11.0	42.9	3.88

Conclusions

In identifying a FBSE data subset, linking it to publicly available OFLC PERM data, and successfully enriching it with publication details from WoS, we built a robust process to create a rich data set consisting of information on FBSEs' education background, career trajectories, and research contributions. An assessment of the resulting data set confirmed the high-quality of the data, despite some representation challenges, which reflect, in part, the existing biases of the 2016-2019 OFLC PERM data set selected for our proof of concept.

We have demonstrated that it is possible to create a high-quality data set suitable for analysis, albeit of a limited group of FBSEs who entered the US through visa categories that were dominated by H-1B (highly specialized temporary workers) and L-1 (intracompany transferees) visas. This experience highlights the value of access to the full range of entry visas to create data sets that are representative of the FBSE population in the US.

This problem of lack of full representation of the FBSE population is not unique to our data set. As noted in NSF's Science and Engineering Indicators report¹¹ the analysis of FBSE is often conducted by visa type. For instance, the analysis of foreign-born undergraduates is based on individuals who entered the US on F-1 (student) visas whereas the analysis of individuals with more advanced degrees includes individuals who entered the US on J-1 (exchange visitor) visas.